

MADRAS

D2.4 Development of IMHyPE and thermoforming - 1

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Executive summary

Deliverable 2.4 - *Report about the development of IMHyPE and thermoforming - 2* exposes advances related to WP2 - T2.3 - *Plastic processing*. It is a continuation of the work exposed in first release of the deliverable (D2.2), related to the thermoforming and/or over-moulding process on selected substrates for demonstrators and active components as antennas and organic photodetectors (OPD).

Regarding antennas, compatibility of the selected thermoplastic for injection, TPU, with cellulose nanofibrils (CNF) foils has been analysed. Firstly, it has been proved that a reduction of the thickness of the TPU layer avoid cracking of the CNF upon bending. Secondly, adhesion between both materials has been addressed by testing different grades of CNF: with additional coatings like PVDC, PU and others, with different grades of roughness obtained by μ -embossing and with new grade of nanocellulose with sorbitol.

For injection moulding process of the tag a mould with a cavity to host the MCU was manufactured. Several injection tests were conducted to optimize injection parameters.

Regarding fingerprint sensor, the thermoforming tests on the PI/TPU/PC stack presented in D2.2 has continued. These initial set of experiments has enabled to test the resistance of the stack of substrate materials to the shape of demo 2 mould. During this period, the resistance to strain of deposited MoCr lines was evaluated. Test structures containing TFT and OPD has been used to test the resistance of these devices to pressure and temperature applied during the thermoforming and injection moulding step. Finally, the injection mould for the fingerprint sensor has been designed.

The partners participating in this task are EUT, TNO, INF, UWL and AWCP. D2.4 summarizes the most relevant results exposed in D2.4 and exposes the work carried out from month 15 to month 20.

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List of abbreviations

Ag NW	Silver nanowires
AWCP	Arjowiggings
<i>e</i>	Thickness
ETR	eCooltra
EUT	Eurecat
GNK	Genesink
IGZO	Indium gallium zinc oxide
IME	In-mould electronics
INF	InfinityPV
CNF	Cellulose nanofibrils-Nanofibrillated cellulose
NCF	Nanocellulose foil
NP	Nanoparticles
OLAE	Organic and large area electronics
OPD	Organic photodetector
PAL	Photoactive layer
PC	Polycarbonate
PCE	Power conversion efficiency
PI	Polyimide
PMMA	Polymethylmethacrylate
R_c	Radius of curvature
R_s	Sheet resistance
SMD	Surface mount device
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
TPU	Thermoplastics polyurethane
UHF	Ultra-High Frequency
UWB	Ultra-Wide Band
UWL	Uwinloc
WP	Work package

Introduction

MADRAS project addresses the need for innovative and industrial manufacturing processes for the development of robust series of flexible plastronics products. In Mould Electronics (IME) will be validated as a high-speed and competitive manufacturing methodology, building up on an already established mass production technology as plastic injection. To do so, four high performance materials are developed in MADRAS to be applied in the IME manufacturing approach tackling high cost, instability, and short lifetime of OLAE devices.

MADRAS materials and production process will be validated in two different demonstrators, including a biometric photosensor for user identification and a geotracking flexible tag for the Industry 4.0 sector.

The geotracking tag will consist in a flexible foil based on nanocellulose with a combination of printed antennas (UHF and UWB), a small rigid multipoint control unit part (MCU) and additional SMD components, if necessary. Both parts will be fully integrated into a flexible plastic piece through an overmoulding process. For the geotracking tag, the most important requirements will be the flexibility and transparency to radiofrequency. Therefore, TPU or related flexible thermoplastic will be the preferred choice.

The biometric sensor will be integrated as an IME device in the body part around the dashboard of a scooter from a vehicle sharing company. The integration process will consist in firstly, the attaching of a flexible sensor on a polymer substrate, which will be then thermoformed into the desired shape, and overmoulded. The injection process will allow for an enhanced integration of the fingerprint sensor on the motorbike body, therefore thermoplastic as polycarbonate (PC), widely used in automotive industry for its impact resistance, will be desired.

Therefore, injection moulding will be performed on both demos with the objective of enhancing robustness and durability and protecting the active components and circuit elements.

Purpose of the document

This document aims to presents the work carried out regarding Task *T2.3 - Plastic processing* from WP2. Advances from month 8 to 15, already presented in D2.2, are summarized and advances from month 16 to 20 are added. WP2 aims to develop the processing of printed electronic materials and the subsequent incorporation into plastic pieces, together with the electronic circuitry. The specific objectives of this WP are:

- 1) Quality printing of the functional materials and devices by high throughput techniques.
- 2) Design and assembly of components by Pick & Place (P&P) of the electronic components.
- 3) Successful thermoforming and/or injection moulding of the substrates printed with the innovative materials.

The advances towards objectives reflected in the deliverable are the following:

- Develop cellulose nanofibrils (CNF) foil compatible with injection moulding of thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) and set optimized conditions for injection fo the tag with embbbeded MCU.
- Test the resistance to plastic processing of MoCr lines on PI/TPU/PC stack, OPD and TFT structures, building blocks for biometric sensor.
- Thermoforming and injection mould for demo 1 and demo 2 design and manufacturing.

Summary of results from Deliverable D2.2

In the first release of deliverable *D2.2 Report about the development of IMHyPE and thermoforming - 1*, the following results were presented:

- Initial testing of compatibility of injected polymers like thermoplastics polyurethane (TPU) with nanocellulose foils was analysed.
- The redesign of the antennas by simulation considering the presence of a TPU layer of different thickness over the printed UHF antenna was addressed.
- Geometry and position of the demo 2 on the motorbike selected part was defined. A first design for thermoforming and injection mould tool for the fingerprint sensor was drawn. The design and the ergonomics were designed to be compliant, since the very beginning, with the final motorbike-selected part integration.
- A substrate stack for fingerprint sensor was selected which uses a TPU buffer layer between PI carrier and PC. The process of lamination and thermoforming of PI/TPU/PC stack was described. The feasibility of thermoforming of the fingerprint sensor was explored by processing PI/TPU/PC stacks over a mould that resembles the final design. The mould consisted in three mould inserts with different bending angles that were used to compare differences in thermoforming ability of different stacks and define forming limits.
- TFT test structure platform was design by TNO. The platform aims for testing several thermoforming parameters step-wise: pressure and temperature limits, thermoforming of TFT and TFT/OPD full stack.
- Preliminary experiments on plastic injection on OPD were presented with the aim of setting up a platform that enables to study the stability of OPD constituent materials (photoactive layers, charge transport layers, electrodes and encapsulant materials) to injection processes and film/injected polymer compatibility.

1. IME process on Geotracking Tag

1.1 Compatibility test between TPU and CNF

As presented in D2.1, thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) was the selected thermoplastic to be used as the encapsulation material for the geo-tracking tag, being the most used flexible polymer.

The CNF samples were over-injected using a standard mould from EUT with a squared-shape geometry of 70x70 mm². By using interchangeable inserts (orange region in Figure 1) different thicknesses can be injected varying from 1.25 to 4 mm.

Figure 1. Schematics of the mould used for plastic injection experiments. Mechanical subjection of the film (purple) in the mould cavity (grey).

The film inside the mould cavity is subjected mechanically via pins in the injection side of the machine (Figure 1). The molten polymer goes through a hole cut in the film to the other side, covering a square 70x70 mm area. The upper part is finally removed to obtain a square part.

One of the main challenges of injecting the tag is the use of a non-polymer substrate as CNF foils. During first injection test, 2.5 mm was chosen as the TPU thickness to test compatibility with grade 1 CNF. The chosen thermoplastic was TPU Estane Clear 15N80 manufactured by Lubrizol.

As shown in Figure 2, some cracks were revealed on the assembly upon bending. As detailed in D2.1, cracking was associated to differences in elongation at break of both materials, further accentuated due to the relative thicknesses and positions of both materials on the final assembly.

Figure 2. Injection moulding of 2.5 mm TPU on top of CNF foil.

Moreover, adhesion between TPU and film was moderate, being the film easy to pull apart. The following strategies were proposed to improve overall assembly's deformability and adhesion:

- 1) Locate CNF closer the neutral axis during the injection step by TPU's thickness reduction.
- 2) Test Micro fluted CNF foils.
- 3) Test a different grade of TPU with higher adhesion to CNF.
- 4) Use of different coating on CNF foil to improve TPU adhesion.

Use of cellulose plasticizer (during the manufacturing of the NCF) Moreover, throughout WP2 different grades of TPU has been tested. From month 12-20, two grades of TPU were tested: TPU standard (Pearlthane® CLEAR 15N80) and new grade named TPU ECO (Pearlthane™ ECO D12T80E) with increased adhesion and 43% of bio-based content. The ECO grade was firstly chosen as it has higher peel strength values compared to conventional TPU grades: 60 N/cm versus 2 and 9 N/cm from regular Polyether and Polyester TPUs. In fact, TPU can be divided in two groups: Polyester-based and Polyether-based. No apparent different in adhesion was observed with the two TPU under test. Finally, the final choice for Madras' geotracking tags was a pure polyether-based TPU named TPU ESTANE® 58214 NAT 055, since it provides a higher hydrolysis resistance.

1.2 Strategies to improve in-mould assembly's deformability and adhesion

1.2.1 Location of CNF foil closer to the neutral axis by reduction of TPU thickness

Printed antennas have been over-injected with TPU with the lowest available thickness for the mould in use: 1.25 mm. As depicted in Figure 3, the reduction of the injected TPU to 1.25 mm prevented cracking of CNF upon bending, and as shown in Figure 3-right, the film only cracked after harsh bending. As discussed previously, the effect of cracking has been reduced due to a closer location of the foil to the neutral axis.

Figure 3. Bending test for 1.25mm-injected TPU samples.

1.2.2 Comparison between CNF with different roughness and TPU

Adhesion strategy through mechanical bonding of injected plastic with CNF foils was inspected by testing foils with different grades of roughness. The technique of μ -embossing was used by AWCP to produce different degrees of roughness on samples. Samples tested had 6 different grades of μ -embossing, labelled 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000 and 1200. Samples were labelled according to the grain density according to FEPA (Federation of European Producers of Abrasives) where correspondence from grain size to mean grain size in μm is: 200 = 75 μm ; 400 = 35 μm ; 600 = 25.8 μm ; 800 = 21.8 μm ; 1000 = 18.3 μm and 1200 = 15.3 μm . At the same time, two grades of TPU were tested: TPU standard (15N80) and new grade named TPU ECO (D12T80E).

TPU 15N80

TPU D12T80E eco

Figure 4. In-mould antennas printed with HC Ag NP ink on different grades of CNF (grade 1, micro-embossed) and injected with two different grades of TPU (15N80 and D12T80E).

Table 1 shows the parameters applied for the injection moulding experiment:

		Parameters	TPU 15N80 (1.25 mm)	TPU D12T80E (1.25 mm)
Barrel temp	Nozzle [°C]		195	210
	Metering zone [°C]		210	215
	compression zone [°C]		200	210
	feeding zone [°C]		195	200
Mould temp	Injection side temp [°C]		35	35
	Ejection side temp [°C]		35	35
Injection unit	Metering stroke [mm]		40	40
	Pressure Limit. [bar]		2400	2400
	Peak Inj. Pressure[bar]		986	1165
	Injection speed [mm/s]		60	80
	Compression force [bar]		200	200
	Compression time [s]		10	10
	Cooling time [s]		4	3,48
	Switch-over point [mm]		15	16
	Cushion [mm]		14.8	14.7
	Backpressure [Bar]		30	60

Table 1 . Parameters for TPU injection moulding process with TPU15N80 and TPU D12T80E.

Moderate adhesion between TPU and CNF foil was found in all the grades of μ -embossing discarding this strategy for adhesion improvement.

On the other side, as depicted in Figure 4-(right), the appearance of bubbles between printed tracks and CNF substrate on samples injected with the new TPU (D12T80E) was observed. Formation of air bubbles could be related to porosity of the CNF, an insufficient drying of the CNF foils or non-yet optimized injection moulding process conditions.

Additionally, bubbles were only observed on printed areas indicating a better adhesion of the printed layer to TPU than to the foil. In fact, in this set of samples antennas were printed with Highly Conductive Ag NP ink, which we know had poor adhesion to CNF. After these results, EUT, UWL and GNK agreed to continue demo 1 development with Increased Adhesion Ag NP ink despite the detriment in conductivity.

Finally, the whole assembly showed some warping probably due to the difference in surface tension between the TPU and the nanocellulose substrate. To avoid the excessive warping, various injection parameters were modified: lower back pressure value, higher back pressure time and higher switch-over position. These parameters allow the polymer-CNF interface to release stresses before being ejected from the mould, correcting the warping. The higher switch-over point allows the part to still be filled even when the compression force after injection is lower. Table 2 shows the variation in mentioned parameters.

Parameters	First injection condition	Second injection condition
Back pressure (bar)	200	50
Back pressure time (s)	10	15
Switch-over point (mm)	15	16,5

Table 2. Parameters optimization to avoid warping.

1.2.3 Use of different coating layers and plasticizer for adhesion improvement to TPU

First iteration: injection on PVDC-coated CNF and CNF plasticized with sorbitol

As a first approach, CNF with PVDC coating was developed by AWCP to planarize CNF. PVDC was chosen because of its high surface energy that will allow post-printing and also due to its barrier against moisture properties.

By testing injection moulding on PVDC coated foils, it was observed that PVDC had better adhesion to TPU than to CNF. As depicted in Figure 5, mechanical peeling was done on a sample injected with TPU on an antenna printed on PVDC-coated CNF, including a hybridized PCB (see results of this experiment in section 1.2). PVDC layer, printed tracks and glued PCB were better adhered to TPU than to CNF. PVDC layer remained on the surrounding CNF (use for holding the sample in the mould) where no plastic was injected.

Figure 5. Mechanical peeling performed on an in-mould assembly of sample printed on PVDC-coated CNF. The transfer of PVDC layer with the printed antenna was observed.

Injection of TPU was also tested on the last developed substrate, phosphorylated CNF with 20% of sorbitol additive. Sorbitol was also introduced as a plasticizer to reduce the foil stiffness and it also resulted in the higher degree of transparency achieved until now. No adhesion could be achieved with the transparent grade of CNF.

Figure 6. Testing of TPU overmoulding on phosphorylated CNF with sorbitol additive.

After this observation, together with first climate chamber test on grade 1 CNF that show poor moisture resistance (see D2.6), encapsulation and adhesion improvement was addressed by: i) coating CNF foils with different PVDC grades to improve the adhesion of PVDC to CNF, ii) coat NCF foil with PU emulsion; iii) coat NCF foils with acrylic or protective coating; iv) PVDC coating in one side (the outside).

PU was chosen because of a probable better compatibility with TPU. Another grade of CNF was fabricated were with PVDC coated just on 1-side. This would allow to have increased (but still moderate) adhesion on the side where there is no PVDC coating and, on the opposite side, exposed to air, take advantage of the barrier against moisture that might provide PVDC layer. Acrylic and protective coating (Loctite) were chosen because AWCP uses it as adhesion layers in other projects.

Table 3 summarises the different samples done.

Base	Polymer used	Polymer reference	Number of A4	Coatweight g/m ²
CNF grade1 52 g/m ²	PVDC	Diofan B203	3	7,5
CNF grade1 52 g/m ²	PVDC	Diofan 193 DH	3	7,5
CNF grade1 52 g/m ²	PVDC	Diofan A297	3	7,5
CNF grade1 52 g/m ²	PVDC	Diofan A50	3	7,5
CNF grade1 52 g/m ²	PU	SEBATRANS 111.840 BK1	3	7,5
CNF grade1 52 g/m ²	Protective coating	Loctite NCI9001	3	from 4 to 20
CNF grade1 52 g/m ²	Acrylic	Lumiled W10	3	7,5

Table 3. Different polymers used as adhesion layer on CNF.

Second iteration: Different grades of PVDC vs PU coating

PU coated CNF showed the best adhesion to injected TPU while all the grades of PVDC gave similar results as the previously found as well as a protective coating and acrylic: PVDC had better adhesion to TPU than to CNF.

Moreover, the NFC grade with 1-side PVDC coating showed curling after curing process which hampered the fixing of the foil in the injection mould. Although this substrate could be a good solution to take benefits of barrier properties of PVDC, care must be taken upon curing. Curling can be prevented by ensuring that printed foils are fixed on the oven plate and by keeping them in foil protectors upon cooling, so they remain plane in all the process.

Third iteration: different grades of PU coating and alternative coating materials

To validate PU-coated CNF, the printability and conductive properties of Ag NP layer was evaluated. Conductive layer of Ag NP couldn't be obtained with 1st batch of PU coated substrates. AWCP proposed and prepared CNF with other coating material and with different thickness of PU and with a grade of PU with an additional crosslink with higher resistance to humidity and temperature. Photonic curing was found as a sintering route to obtain conductive layers on PU coated samples.

As shown in Figure 7, samples of tags were printed with Smart Screen A (Ag NP with Increased Adhesion) on the several substrates. For sintering Ag NP layers, a precuring in the oven at <90°C/10min was done followed by a photonic curing step (pulse at 320 V; 500ms ON/500ms OFF;10 pulses front + 10 back). Finally, samples were inject moulded with TPU to evaluate adhesion. Results at summarized in the following table:

Type of coating	R _q before Photonic curing (mΩ/sq)	R _q after Photonic curing (mΩ/sq)	Adhesion to TPU after injection	Observations
LOCTITE LISSE	1000	272	Poor	Bad film forming
LOCTITE 16	NA	358	Poor	Bad film forming
LOCTITE 43	NA	315	Poor	Bad film forming
LUMILED ST	206	126	Poor	Wrinkled substrate difficult to manipulate, coating shows britleness
PU-16 μm	NA	125	Good	
PU-60 μm	NA	400	Good	
PU-100 μm	NA	325	Good	
PU with crosslinker	NA	87	Good	
PU/PVDC	NA	490	Good	Warping after curing due to different tension in each side
GRADE 1	205	96	Poor	
PET	182	73	Good	

Table 4. Sheet resistance before and after photonic curing Ag NP layers printed on top of NCF foils coated with different materials and adhesion properties of substrates to TPU after injection moulding.

Figure 7. Appearance of printed and in-mould tags of substrates with different coating materials: LOCTITE, LUMILEC and TPU.

On PU-coated samples shown in Figure 7, coatings were done at lab scale by rod coating on 2 sides. Best conductive properties were obtained with PU with 3% of crosslinker but substrates look very wavy due to 2 sides coatings in the lab (CNF is very sensitive to moisture variation).

Fourth iteration: PU coating with pilot coating equipment

To improve roughness of PU-coated samples, pilot coating trials with different structures (1 layer or 2 layers per side) were carried out (with different coat weight of PU: 4 or 8 g/m²). This was done on RK pilot coater at AWCP using reverse roll coating head (Figure 8) with a width of 300 mm.

Figure 8. RK coater at AWCP.

Screen printing of Smart screen A and B from GNK was tested on PU coated CNF grade 1 (4 g/m² on side 1 and 8 g/m² on side 2) and gave the following good results with oven curing:

Ink	Average resistance (@ 6° 110°C)		Average resistance (@ 10° 120°C)		Average resistance (@ 5° 140°C)	
	mΩ/□	SD	mΩ/□	SD	mΩ/□	SD
Smart Screen A	687	170	232	46	139	19
Smart Screen B	144	27	97	12	69	8

Table 5. Electrical resistance of PU coated samples printed with Smart Screen A and B.

As it was noticed that samples with 8 g/m² of PU gives cockles during the curing of the ink (Figure 5), it was decided to continue with the lowest coat weight of PU (4 g/m² per side).

Figure 9. Cockling during curing of the ink on 8 g/m² PU coated CNF

2 other series of PU coated CNF at 4 g/m² per side trials were carried out at AWCP to be able to print silver inks by screen printing as well as roll to roll flexographic printing. Further information about curing conditions for tags can be found in D2.6.

In summary, injected assemblies with 2-side PU coated CNF gives the best results in term of adhesion to TPU. Several roll-to-roll trials were done by AWCP to give samples to the partners of the consortium.

1.3 Injection moulding on hybridized PCB

First trials of TPU injection on an CNF foil with and hybridized PCB were performed and successfully achieved (Figure 10). Results indicate that the injection process on hybridized UWL's MCU should work. A 4 mm thick insert was used for TPU injection, being the CNF foil + PCB assembly 2.75 mm thick.

The PCB with welded connector was used to further characterize the antennas after injection. To do so, firstly a peelable resin was used to protect UFL connector. Connector could be accessed by melting the TPU.

Figure 10. IM-antenna with integrated directly hybridized PCB.

As shown in following schematic, the next step consisted in manufacturing a thinner mould insert with a constant thickness of 1.25 mm and a 4 mm rectangular section to host the PCB named cavity.

Figure 11. Schematic of the mould used for injection experiment on hybridized PCB (left) and the final aspect that assembly will have by using the mould with a cavity in preparation (right).

The design of the in-mould cavity considers the simulated thickness of 1.25 mm on top of the printed elements in order to prevent the antenna to lose performance. For that reason, the cavity section is only bigger around the control unit area.

Mould cavity design and injection parameters optimization

In contrast with the preliminary tests with the 4 mm thick insert, the 1.25 mm thick insert performed, initially, worse. The reduction of thickness and the cross-section change between the PCB area and the rest of the tag sharply rose the shear stress produced by the polymer in the CNF substrate, resulting in the ripping of the film right above the control unit (Figure 12). Test samples produced with PET substrate did not have the same issue, probably due to PET's higher tensile strength, concluding that the current insert geometry was not appropriate for a CNF substrate.

Figure 12. Ripping of the substrate, above the control unit. The ripping always occurs in the same spot.

To prevent the ripping of the substrate, changes in the cavity design were made, as well as optimizing injection parameters:

- Cavity design: cross-section flow change was softened by adding chamfers on the walls.

Figure 13. Original mold cavity (left). Modified cavity (right)

Figure 14. Cross-section detail. Above: original cavity. Below: modified.

The modified cavity design consists of a small insert (dark blue in Figure 14) that can be modified to accommodate later versions of the control unit with bigger components. The PCB cavity was initially machined to be 2 mm tall from the centre line, since the first control unit dummies were only 1 mm thick, maintaining a constant ~1 mm section across the tag. Once the final control units were manufactured, the small insert was modified to be 4 mm tall, still maintaining the 1 mm thickness.

- Parameter optimization: experiments were carried on a big batch of antennas to optimize the injection process parameters once the cavity modification was done. It was concluded that a higher melting temperature along with a higher injection speed provided the best results and prevented the substrate from ripping. Higher injection temperatures made the polymer more fluid and thus produced less shear stress on the surface of the substrate. Higher injection speed caused the cavity to fill faster and reduced the time the polymer applies shear stress.
- Finally, a lower back pressure allowed the tag to sit flat instead of warping. It is believed that the previous value compacted the part too much, which produced combing.

Figure 15. Higher back pressure (up) and lower back pressure (down)

A table with the change of parameters is presented below:

Parameter	Original value	Modified value
T° zone 1 (°C)	200	220
T° zone 2 (°C)	195	215
T° zone 3 (°C)	190	210
T° zone 4 (°C)	190	200
Injection speed (mm/s)	5	150
Back pressure (bar)	500	150

Table 6. Injection mold parameters modification.

Figure 16. Microscope photographs of ripped samples using the original injection parameters (left) and samples without ripping using the modified values (right)

The next injection mould iteration was performed with semi-final control units, using the optimized parameters. Results proved that the injection molding values yielded reproducible results, preventing again the ripping of the substrate. Results regarding the last injection batch with final control units are presented in WP3 document.

2. IME process on fingerprint sensor

2.1 Thermoforming process

The fingerprint sensor is built up on a glass carrier. First a thin layer of polyimide (PI) is spin coated on the glass substrate. Next the functional layers of the device are added. Eventually, the glass carrier may be removed afterwards. Unfortunately, PI is a non-stretchable substrate. When thermoforming a fingerprint sensor, bending is possible. Stretching, however, is more difficult, as the PI substrate can hardly be stretched (which is due to its high Young's modulus). Local stress and strain induced to PI will cause wrinkling.

An intermediate layer was introduced to the stack to work as a buffer layer. The use of TPU between PI and PC 'absorbs' the deformation that builds up in the stack avoiding wrinkling of the PI, and also adheres to both PI and PC.

Experiments are performed to give insight in the thermoforming shapes that can be applied, without destroying the structural integrity of the fingerprint sensors. The feasibility of thermoforming the fingerprint sensor can be explored by processing 'dummy' devices over a mould that resembles the final design described in section 2.1, but with different shape details as shown in Figure 17. These experiments can reveal, which shapes result in well-formed and functional sensor arrays, and which shapes result in defects. Well-performing shapes may be integrated in the final design.

Figure 17. Thermoforming mould resembling final design: a triangular prism with variations in the dihedral angle (30, 40 and 45°).

The mould consists of a baseplate that can be applied with a 3D object with triangular cross section. Hereby, the height and slope of the triangular prism can be varied (by using different inserts), in which the ‘sensor plane’ is placed under an angle of 30, 40 or 45°. The ‘dummy device’, which consists of a 48 x 150 mm PI (Kapton) sample is laminated onto the PC substrate (350 x 260 mm²), using different TPU materials. In all experiments, the PI should bend in only one direction, as bi-directional bending will inevitably lead to wrinkling of the substrate.

The lamination of the PI-Intermediate-PC stack was done with the Optek DPL-24A vacuum laminator (vacuum phase 180 s and pressure phase 300 s) at TNO Holst Centre.

Thermoforming was performed with the Niebling SAMK 400-42 equipment at TNO Holst Centre. Heating step with 310/315/325 °C (three heating zones) and a heating time of 8.5 s. A Forming pressure of 60 bar and a mould temperature of 120 °C. After heating, the sample is transported to the forming position. During this move, the temperature distribution on the (lower) sample surface is recorded. Optimum forming temperature of the PC substrate is 160 - 165 °C. In the area where the PI sample is applied, material thickness is larger; although this results in a lower sample temperature in the ‘PI region’, it does not prevent forming of this section.

2.1.1 Formability of MoCr lines on PI/TPU/PC stack with Niebling system

Before we apply functional samples to a thermoforming experiment, the degree of deformations that can be applied has been determined, and which TPU type and thickness result in the optimum material stack have been tested with a plain PI/TPU/PC stack. The results are described in deliverable D2.2.

The main conclusions are that 1) the angle in the mould shape does not have a large effect on the product quality, 2) using thicker intermediate layers leads to larger temperature differences between the substrate sections, 3) thinner samples show better forming. Overall, the Bemis 3415 (75um) and Platilon 4201AU (100um) TPU show the best results in the thermoforming trials of plain PI substrates.

The next step consists in introducing metal lines on the PI substrate in the same way as will be for the electronic circuit on the final demonstrator (same thickness, width, and application method).

The design of the metal lines is shown Figure 18. As similar for the final fingerprint sensor demonstrator short and long metal lines are created with a thickness of 22 and 37um.

Figure 18. Design of metal lines for thermoforming experiments.

The metal lines are made by sputtering Molybdenum Chromium (MoCr) full area on a PI substrate and patterned with lithography. From these substrates 2 different PI/TPU/PC stacks were made using the Platilon U4201AU (100um) and Bemis 3415 (75um) TPU's. The used PC material Covestro Makrofol DE1-1 with a thickness of 250 μm , for both stacks.

The PI/TPU/PC stacks were thermoformed using the mould described in D2.2. The substrates were placed on the baseplate as shown in Figure 19 and thermoformed using the 40° angle mould insert shown in Figure 20.

Figure 19. Placement of PI/TPU/PC stack on the thermoforming mould. Left; substrates with long metal lines. Right; substrates with short metal lines.

Figure 20. PI/TPU/PC stack formation using the 40° angle mould insert.

The thermoformed stacks were inspected visually by checking if the substrate stack is closely following the shape of the mould insert and if there are wrinkles, air inclusions or other defects occurring. The functionality of the metal lines was also evaluated by measuring the electrical resistance over the line length.

The visual inspection after lamination is shown in Figure 20, and after thermoforming is shown in Figure 21. The functionality result of the lines after lamination and thermoforming are shown in Table 7. Platilon U4201AU (100um) functionality results after lamination and thermoforming. Table 7 and Table 8.

PL1 Some larger wrinkles (probable cause of many broken lines)

PL2 No wrinkles, no defects

BL1 Few small wrinkles (don't result in defects)

BL2 Some wrinkles (probable cause of 5 defect lines)

Figure 21. Visual inspection after lamination. Top; Platilon U4201AU (100 μ m) and Bottom; Bemis 3415 (75 μ m)

PL1 - large delamination in 'inside' bend

BL1 - some wrinkles in 'inside' bend

Figure 22. Visual inspection after thermoforming. Top; Platilon U4201AU (100um) and Bottom; Bemis 3415 (75 μm)

Sample	After lamination		After Thermoforming	
	Broken lines	Functional lines	Broken lines	Functional lines
P_Long1	12	8	20	0
P_long2	0	20	20	0
P_Short1	0	20	20	0

Table 7. Platilon U4201AU (100um) functionality results after lamination and thermoforming.

Sample	After lamination		After Thermoforming	
	Broken lines	Functional lines	Broken lines	Functional lines
B_Long1	0	20	0	20
B_long2	5	15	1	19
B_Short1	0	20	7	13

Table 8. Bemis 3415 (75um) functionality results after lamination and thermoforming.

A general observation is that that there was no difference measured between the reliability of 22 and 37 μm lines. Resistance of functional lines complies with reference values.

The samples prepared with Platilon U4201AU gave poor results. Lamination leads to a high number of line defects, subsequent thermoforming results in failure of all remaining metal lines. The samples prepared with Bemis 3415 gave better results, although not all metal lines remain functional during processing. Lamination leads to some lines failure, thermoforming damages some additional lines. Overall, more than 90 % of the metal lines survive the lamination and thermoforming processing steps.

Samples, prepared with Bemis TPU, also have a better visual quality. Apart from some wrinkling on the samples edges at inner bends of the product, no defects are observed. Samples, prepared with Platilon TPU, show more defects. At inner bends, the material does not closely follow the mould shape. Moreover, delamination on the interface with PC may occur.

It can be concluded that Bemis 3415 (75um) TPU is the better performing ‘stress absorption layer’ for the intended application. Although the Bemis buffer layer does prevent many line failures, not all test samples are fully functional after processing. The Bemis 3415 material will be further optimized to be used as the intermediate layer for thermoforming PI based fingerprint sensor. Further experiments will be done on the TFT Test structures.

2.1.2 Formability of MoCr lines on PI/TPU/PC stack with Illig system

To study the formability of samples with Illig system, another mould was manufactured. The reason being the differences with Niebling system, which works with pressure and temperature, whereas Illig works with vacuum and temperature.

First thermoforming trials were done with PI/TPU laminated samples, with no circuits, to observe the behaviour of the stack during processing. Initial samples showed delamination of the PI/TPU stack around the base of the pyramid and the formation of bubbles between the TPU layer and PI. Parameters were modified to reach three main goals:

1. Good part definition, within PC’s thermoformability T° range
2. Avoid formation of bubbles: it was observed that increased T° formed more bubbles
3. Avoid PI delamination, caused by low thermoforming T°

Different temperature distributions across the sheet were tested. Temperature distributions allow for the surrounding sheet to be heated to optimal thermoforming T° without overheating the central stack and prevent bubbles from appearing. Figure 23 shows a schematic of the heating plate T° distribution. Wide T° ranges (440-390-440) caused severe delamination because of the T° difference between the central, 390°C PI stack and the rest of the sheet. Low T° ranges (410-380-410) caused minimum delamination but not good part definition. At the end, a homogenous T° distribution of 410°C across the sheet yielded best results in terms of minimum delamination and formation of bubbles, although the latter could not be avoided.

Figure 23. T° distribution within the heating plate. Central T2° corresponds with the stack’s position and is aligned with it.

Additional observations on the delamination effect were done with a thermographic camera to study the temperature variations within the substrate. Four points were defined (Figure 24):

- SP1: centre of the PI stack, right above vacuum point.
- SP2: Tail of PI stack.
- SP3: border of PI stack, right above vacuum point where delamination is prominent.
- SP4: PC substrate.

After heating plates are removed and the film is pulled to the mould's surface, points above the vacuum rim (SP1 and SP3) take longer to cool down since they are not touching the mould. Specifically, the centre point (SP1) seems to keep the heat longer than SP3, probably because the latter is influenced by the change of substrate (to PC).

However, during the vacuum phase, points SP1 and SP3 cool down faster than the rest of the substrate. The cooling rate is not enough to stop the PC substrate to be pulled towards the pyramid, but it might be too low for the PI stack to follow along. The vacuum rim location, away from the pyramid base, fixates the substrate, adding difficulty to the movement. This is the reason why delamination of samples generates in the borders and is only observed in the base of the pyramid.

Figure 24. Left: Thermographic picture of the thermoforming mould assembly. Study point T° were: SP1: 118,2°C; SP2: 74,6°C; SP3: 86,4°C; SP4: 78,7°C. Right: Sample with delamination occurring on the sides of the PI stack, in the base of the pyramid.

Figure 25. time dependent temperature graphic extracted from the thermographic camera analysis during a thermoforming cycle. It can be seen how SP1 and SP3 T° values remain high but drop substantially once vacuum phase starts.

With the input of those observations, changes in the mould vacuum points were done. The original vacuum point was located away from the pyramid base, instead of the base rim. This provoked the sheet to need a high T° to be pulled towards the pyramid. A schematic of this phenomenon can be seen in Figure 26. Regarding the different angle inserts (35° , 40° and 45°), the 35° degrees insert provided best results since the deformation needed to form the pyramid is less than the 40° and 45° inserts.

Next thermoforming trials proved that the new vacuum system prevented the delamination effect from happening.

Figure 26. Left: schematic of the film behavior (yellow line) when being pulled by vacuum forces against the mold (gray). The vacuum rim is signaled with a blue line. Right: repositioning of the vacuum lines closer to the pyramid base.

Before thermoforming, samples were characterized to ensure that conductivity had not been lost during transportation. All samples' values matched those provided by TNO. The 35-degree insert was used since it yielded best results in prior experiments. Thermoforming parameters are listed in Table 9 below.

Parameters	Units	Value	Value	Value
Heating (sup)	-	-	-	-
Zone 1	°C	410	410	410
Zone 2	°C	410	410	410
Zone 3	°C	410	410	410
Heating (inferior)	-	-	-	-
Zone 1	°C	480	480	480
Zone 2	°C	480	480	480
Zone 3	°C	480	480	480
Heating time	s	8	7	6

Table 9. Thermoforming parameters

During thermoforming, the sheet heating time was modified as follows:

- Heating time 8/7.5 seconds: good thermoformability but formation of bubbles due to extended heating exposure time.
- Heating time 7 seconds: optimum results, no bubble formation.
- Heating time 6 seconds: no bubbles, but bad thermoformability.

Figure 27. Samples with different heating times. From left to right: 8s, 7s and 6.5s.

Contrary to what expected, bubble formation in samples was not observed to be related to loss of functionality. Figure 28 shows the bubble cluster across the pyramid's spine. These bubbles did not affect the integrity of the electronic circuits as conductivity on lines could be measured.

Figure 28: Close up of bubble formation across the spine of the pyramid.

It is believed that creases present in samples are formed due to the mobility of TPU below the PI by the action of heat. A sample that presented creases before thermoforming was exposed to a heating cycle (without vacuum) and it was observed that creases disappeared and, consequently, some circuits regained functionality. This proved that the TPU below the PI has high mobility when being heated. If the TPU lamination is not homogeneous, exposure to heat might help to the formation of bubbles and/or creases. In summary, sample functionality was not lost due to bubble formation. Samples with severe bubble formation remained functional, whereas those with creases (formed before or after thermoforming) lose it.

Figure 29. Sample exposed to a heating cycle. The observed crease disappears after being heated. Sample partially regains functionality.

2.1.3 Resistance of OPDs to heating cycles in a thermoformer

In order to tackle resistance of OPD to temperature to ensure successful plastic processing, an experiment has been conducted where reference OPD fabricated on ITO/glass substrates, has been heated up with infrared heater from EUT thermoforming machine.

Additionally, OPD were previously encapsulated by TNO with selected encapsulation process. TNO's barrier stack concept can be found on most of the handheld AMOLED display devices such as smart phones and smart watches. The barrier stack consists of 2 high quality thin film barrier layers composed of amorphous silicon nitride (SiN) with a much thicker organic separation layer in between (organic coating for planarization, OCP). The WVTR of SiN/OCP/SiN was shown to be $WVTR \ll 10^{-6} \text{ g/m}^2/\text{day}$.

This encapsulant layer is expected to be deposited on top of the OPD sensor in final demo. The thermoformed stack will be overmoulded with injected polymer on its back side, leaving the OPD sensor towards the outside with thin encapsulation layer on top to enable fingerprint recognition.

Performance of OPD was evaluated after different heating cycles. Table 10 shows the time steps and temperature used to achieve desired temperatures between 120 °C and 180 °C.

Time on sample (sec)	Temp. heater (°C)	Temp. Reached on sample (°C)
14	500	125
20	500	150
25	500	170
27	500	180

Table 10. Calibration of temperature reached on glass samples after defined heating time step.

Figure 30. Thermographic camera image of evaluated samples right after infrared heating cycle.

The testing was performed on 6 samples of composed by 3 different active layers (PTQ10:IDIC; PTQ10:Y6 and PTQ10:Y12) deposited on glass/ITO substrates (Figure 32-left). Samples were firstly encapsulated at TNO and then tested with the thermoforming equipment at EUT. Before this experiment, EQE of samples after encapsulation was determined (Figure 31). All the samples had good performing OPD with EQE around 60%.

Figure 31. EQE of reference samples after encapsulation at TNO measured at -2V.

Before and after heating cycles, samples were characterized using a Keithley 2602A and a High-power 656 nm LED (from Mightex) as illumination source working at a power of 20 mW/cm². Three to five devices for each 24-pixel sample were characterized after each cycle and power conversion efficiency (PCE) was used as the comparing parameter. Results are gathered in Figure 32.

It was observed that thermoforming conditions corresponding to 125-150 °C yielded to higher PCE for the six samples tested. Slight reduction was detected over 170 °C.

Figure 32 - Box plot of power conversion efficiency (PCE) of several devices included in 24-pixel samples (left). Samples were made of 3 different PAL (PTQ10:IDIC, PTQ10:Y6 and PTQ10:Y12) and heated up with thermoformer machine at specific temperatures between 25 and 175°C.

All in all, this experiment validated in principle the resistance of OPD and encapsulation layer thermoforming to heating steps. A more representative experiment should be tested on samples on TNO's test structures transferred to a plastic substrate where heating time to reach selected temperature will be shorter than for samples on glass-based substrates.

2.2 Plastic processing on OPD/TFT test structures

As presented in *Deliverable 2.2 - section 2.2.2 - TFT structures for thermoforming tests*, TNO has designed a TFT test structure platform to test the effect of plastic processing on TFTs and OPDs. The idea is to probe the OPDs and TFT after the thermoforming and injection moulding processes in a full stack structure. This is the closest we can get to the final prototype.

Figure 33. TFT test structure composed by 3 TFTs/OPD (top) and 4 TFTs (bottom).

Test structures contains 4 single transistors, on the bottom side, and 3 TFT/OPD 50 um pixel arrays, on the top side. The leads are long and placed on the right side. This is done so we can thermoform only the area where the devices are, keeping the leads flat for convenient contacting. On the top side, we can probe the 3 OPD arrays on the TFT/OPD arrays. Each one has an individual bottom contact and a common top contact. The top TFT array can be also probed. The 4 bottom TFTs on the bottom side can be probed independently. For preliminary plastic processing testing we decided to use a 7x7 cm flat mould design at EUT. First step for in-mould processing is the lamination of test structures on selected stack of TPU/PC and the cut in the 7x7 mould shape.

Figure 34. 7x7 cm cut design for injection mould experiment (left), test structures laminated on TPU and PC.

The lamination procedure consists in debonding test structures from glass and laminate them on a TPU/PC substrate. Best result in terms of sample flatness were obtained using a 2 step lamination (results shown in photograph in Figure 34):

1. Laminate first the BEMIS TPU on PC with the cover foil still on the TPU for support. Lamination at 110 °C with 180 sec vacuum and 120 sec pressure.
2. Remove the cover foil and laminate as a second step the PI substrate with TFT/OPD test structures at the same conditions.

After lamination, the samples underwent a thermoforming step, without actually changing the shape of the PC substrate. The thermoforming was done by first heating of the sample to 165 °C by IR, subsequently the sample is move rapidly above the mould with a temperature of the mould set at 120 °C, a pressure of 60 bar was applied for 5 sec.

As a final step, injection moulding was performed at 4 different conditions: Two injection temperatures (265 - 275 °C) and two injection speeds (30 - 70 mm/s). As shown in Table 11, lower injection speed and lower temperature leads to lower injection peak pressure.

We chose a low injection temperature in order to avoid degradation of OPD due to high temperature. 265 °C is considered a low temperature for PC injection but samples resulted in good appearance.

Sample	T (°C)	V (mm/s)	P (Bar)
P4.1	265	30	789
P4.2	265	70	1039
P4.5	275	30	667
P4.7	275	70	919
P4.8	265	30	774
P4.9	265	70	1063
P4.10	275	30	749
P4.11	275	70	928
P4.12	265	30	777

Table 11. Injection parameters for injected Plate 4 (P4) test structures.

Figure 35. Test structure back-injected with PC in a 7x7cm-squared mould.

Figure 36. TFT transfer characteristics of two selected device where the TFT remained functional upon processing.

TFT were measured after each processing: while on glass, after lamination, after applying thermoforming conditions of temperature and pressure, and after injection moulding. Two examples are depicted in Figure 36. TFT transfer characteristics of two selected device where the TFT remained functional upon processing. It should be noted that most TFTs at various stages for testing showed sometimes a larger deviation between transfer curves due to a leaky gate dielectric present in the TFT, in combination with relatively large overlap between bottom and top gate metal structures. This resulted in variable TFT performance, even when performing multiple sweeps on a single device, or even in a short circuit and a failed device. This TFT analysis is further elaborated in Deliverable 2.5.

An overview of samples and devices undergoing all the process steps is provided in Table 12. Overview of simples and devices on Plate 4 (Table 11) undergoing all the IME process steps.

Identifier			Lamination and thermoforming				Injection moulding conditions				Outcome	
Batch	Plate	Sample	TFT characteristics initial	Lamination	Thermoforming	TFT	T (C)	v (mm/s)	P (bar)	with OPD	Functional TFTs	Functional OPD
SA061	4	1	variable	PC/BEMIS 110C (1 step)	P&T (165IR/120C/60bar)	1 ok	265	30	789	yes	1	yes
SA061	4	2	variable, 1 ok	PC/BEMIS 110C (2 steps)	P&T (165IR/120C/60bar)	1 ok	265	70	1039	yes	1	yes
SA061	4	3	bad									
SA061	4	4	bad									
SA061	4	5	low Vt, 2 ok	PC/BEMIS 110C (2 steps)	P&T (165IR/120C/60bar)	4 ok	275	30	667		1	
SA061	4	6	shorts/microscopy									
SA061	4	7	4 ok, spread	PC/BEMIS 110C (2 steps)	P&T (165IR/120C/60bar)	1 ok	275	70	919		1	
SA061	4	8	3 ok	PC/BEMIS 110C (2 steps)		2 ok	265	30	774	yes	0	yes
SA061	4	9	3 curves spread Vt	PC/BEMIS 110C (2 steps)		3 ok	265	70	1063		3	
SA061	4	10	3 curves spread Vt	PC/BEMIS 110C (2 steps)		3 ok	275	30	749		2	
SA061	4	11	3 curves spread Vt	PC/BEMIS 110C (2 steps)		3 ok	275	70	928		2	
SA061	4	12	2 ok	PC/BEMIS 110C (2 steps)		3 ok	265	30	777		2	

Table 12. Overview of simples and devices on Plate 4 (Table 11) undergoing all the IME process steps.

In conclusion, all processing resulted in functional TFTs. The change in TFT transfer curve characteristics varied between processing steps, but moreover also between TFTs. In particular, we observed:

- increased off-current for all devices
- decreased on-current after injection moulding at 275 °C
- V_t shift to 0: only when (after lamination) the $V_t < -5$ V (improvement of TFT)
- observed hysteresis in some of the TFT characteristics seems to be random with conditions, likely due to variable TFT performance

The final experiment will be performed on OPD build on MoCr/IGZO substrates with frontplane made of active layer/HTL/TCE/encapsulant stack. However, the encapsulant solution will be developed in WP3 and the results will be reported in Deliverable D3.2.

2.3 Fingerprint sensor Thermoforming and Injection mould manufacturing

After exploring the feasibility of thermoforming of the fingerprint sensor on a prism-like mould with different angles, the final design, was defined. Dimensions of the pyramid were adapted to selected fingerprint sensor size as shown in Figure 37.

Figure 37. Thermoforming mould resembling final design.

Advancements in the injection moulding inserts of the photodetector demonstrator have been made. The part has been designed to be injected on the back plane of the film, so the melted polymer does not go over the electronic stack. The purpose is to prevent damage to the samples by the high temperatures of injection moulding and shear stress caused by polymer flow. Instead, a later hard coat is proposed to protect the electronic stack.

Figure 39. Injection mould insert (left) and final assembly (right).

Figure 40. 3D-manufactured inserts placed in their respective mold sides; injection (left) and expulsion (right).

In Figure 39 a rectangular pink insert can be observed. The aim is to act as a cushion for the electronic tail to absorb part of the clamping force from the injection mould machine, which could potentially damage the stack. This insert is made from TPU. Its functionality will be tested in future injections.

3. Conclusions and perspectives

While CNF and TPU constitute an appropriate material pair for the antenna printing and in-mould encapsulant (both in terms of compatibility and appropriate antenna's performance), care will need to be taken in order to optimize the assembly's adherence and flatness (avoid warping). Therefore, careful optimization of the pre-process and injection moulding conditions has been performed through WP2.

Although for OPD development and to fulfil objective 1 transparent nanocellulose is imperative and clearly, the use of sorbitol has led to the best results in terms of transparency until now, for geotracking tag demo, which is to be injected with a flexible plastic like TPU, transparency can be disregarded. Thus, for tag development, we have been working with different grades of CNF (grade1, u-embossed, or phosphorylated NCF with sorbitol) or applying different polymer coatings (PVDC, PU and others) as two routes were explored to achieve adhesion to injected TPU: i) mechanical bounding which could be enhanced by using rough CNF foils (u-embossed) or ii) by chemical bonding using polymer coatings.

A 4 g/m² PU coating per side on CNF foil seems to be compatible with injection of TPU and with Ag NP sintering. Several iterations for the improvement of PU-coating were done to obtain Ag NP layer with targeted conductivity. In summary, injected assemblies with 2-side PU coated CNF gave the best results in term of: i) adhesion to TPU, ii) processability of the substrate (less pronounced rolling up of sample after curing); iii) elasticity upon bending and iii) protection to humidity (see D.2.6).

For injection moulding process of the tag a mould with a cavity to host the MCU was manufactured. In that way TPU thickness surrounding the MCU could be reduced to 1.25 mm. On first injection tests ripping of the CNF substrate was observed and so, changes in the cavity design were made, as well as optimization injection parameters. It was concluded that a higher melting temperature along with a higher injection speed provided the best results and prevented the substrate from ripping and gave enhanced flatness.

Regarding plastic processing development for demo 2, it has been demonstrated that the thermoforming stack constituted by PI-TPU-PC fulfils both the requirements needed for the sensor manufacturing (transferring from glass to PI) and those of the final IME process (best adhesion of injected PC onto PC films). Appropriate buffer layer and processing conditions has been defined in order to avoid defects.

During this period the defined stack was tested with deposited metal (MoCr) tracks on PI (simulating the electric circuit in the fingerprint sensor) and TNO's vacuum plug assisted thermoforming. From the two previous TPU's selected described in D2.2, Bemis 3415 (75um) showed the best performance, where more than 90% of the metal lines survived all the processing steps.

Same thermoforming experiments on MoCr/PI/TPU/PC stack was reproduced at Eurecat with Illig high pressure forming to compare thermoforming conditions with the two most common techniques used in industry. Due to Illig's thermoforming process, which uses temperature and vacuum, the sample needed to reach a higher temperature to be thermoformed. Higher temperatures caused the formation of bubbles even with low heating times, concluding that thermoforming demo 2 samples with the Illig system was not optimal.

Test structures containing TFT and OPD were used to validate the TFT after the thermoforming and injection moulding processes in a full stack structure. This is the closest we can get to the final prototype. TFT were measured after each processing: while on glass, after lamination, after applying thermoforming conditions of temperature and pressure, and after injection moulding. All processing resulted in functional TFTs,

4. Risk analysis

The table presented below describes the potential risk and deviations during the project and the contingency plan that would minimize the risk related to the deliverable D2.4.

Risk description	Likelihood	Contingency plan	Who/Actions
Ag NW ink doesn't achieve the expected conductivity and transparency	Medium	Mixture of NW with NPs, curing by different techniques or tuning the thickness of the coating	GNK/Ag NPs based inks were developed for antennas applications (higher conductivity), Ag NW ink coating has been optimized to get the better compromised between transparency and conductivity.
WOx does not achieve the expected conductivity values, mobility and transparency	Medium	Mixture with dopants, curing by different techniques	GNK/ Try to reformulate the WO3 nanoparticle-based ink without the acidic binder. Develop hybrid PEDOT:PSS/WO3 ink without such acidic binder.
New formulations of PEDOT doesn't achieve expected values for hole mobility	Medium	Mixture with dopants and reformulation with different solvents	Nothing to report.
Printed antennas do not show expected impedance / conductivity	Low	Print with alternative nanoparticles inks prepared within the consortium. Use advanced sintering techniques such as photonic and NIR laser curing.	Mitigate since beginning of the project.
Crumpling of the nanocellulose foil during processing, or sensitivity to operational temperature	Medium	Change the solvent of the inks, use laser etching, and alternative curing methods. Work under 150°C	Not detected.
OPD stack with printed electrodes does not reach required dark current and EQE	Medium	Use evaporated HTL and top electrodes for demo 2. HTL and conductive inks developed in MADRAS (PEDOT, hybrid, WO3, AgNW) would then be applied on OPD/OPV.	TNO/ Revise dark current requirements for application in final demo. Chose best HTL/top electrode combination for fingerprint sensor. EUT/ Develop OPD/OPV on flexible substrate using MADRAS' inks and substrates.
Low compatibility between the injection moulding	High	Use of rough (less transparent) NCF for application in Demo 1	The final solution found has been to add a PU coating on NCF which has

Risk description	Likelihood	Contingency plan	Who/Actions
material and the printed device			<p>good adhesion both to NCF and to injected TPU.</p> <p>Use of rough NCF and μ-embossing strategies were tested but it did not result in an increase of adhesion.</p>
Reproducibility of the SMD process	Medium	Redesign of the foil, reallocate the components in the optoelectronics -identify the worse scenario and check that the process is still embedding the components.	Nothing to report.
In-mould antenna does not achieve enough water moisture resistance	Medium	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use a protective coating on exposed side of NCF substrate. 2. Test different grade PVDC, that require different thermal conditions and possess different water moisture resistance; 3. Use an injected thermoplastic with low OTR and VWTR; 4. Use a moisture resistant adhesive to NCF. 	<p>EUT/ Search for thermoplastics with water moisture resistance.</p> <p>ARJO/ Fabrication of CNF with 1 side protective coating layers as PVDC is ongoing</p> <p>Update: The final stack uses PU-coated CNF foils and TPU. PU emulsion used for coating of the CNF has a cross-linker that helps to resist temperature and humidity. The chosen TPU for final tag was ESTANE® 58125 NAT 055, a pure ether grade of TPU with enhanced resistance to hydrolysis.</p>
Delays in delivery of assets (all)	Low	Day to day coordination of the activities to prevent it	Nothing to report.
Unforeseen conflict between partners (IPR issues, etc) or defaulting party (all)	Low	Build professional working relationships, Signature of Consortium Agreement beforehand, with provision of legal basis for conflict resolutions or/and defaulting mechanisms.	Nothing to report.

Table 13. Risk Analysis